

THE TESTING OF ORIENTED POLYETHYLENE FOR BALLISTIC PROTECTION APPLICATIONS: PART A - HIGH STRAIN RATE TESTING PORTION

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ABSTRACT

Oriented polyethylene sheet has been made by a forging process (radial compression) for the Canadian Department of National Defence to evaluate the possibility of using this material for ballistic protection applications. Static and dynamic testing was conducted at Defence Research Establishment Valcartier and the University of British Columbia in comparison with established ballistic protection composites such as Spectra 900 composites. The testing indicated that the oriented polyethylene made by the forging process had similar properties to Spectra 900 composites. Further work needs to be done and this additional work is justified by the results to date.

INTRODUCTION

I.M. Ward [1]-[8] of Leeds University and R.T. Woodhams [9]-[12] of the University of Toronto, have shown that there are several ways to orient polymers. These are in addition to the gel-spinning process used by Allied-Signal and DSM to make the oriented polyethylene fibre which is currently used in ballistic protection applications.

The term oriented polymer refers to the state of the polymer molecule where the polymer chain is not only in a straight line configuration, but also an extensive stress has been applied to elongate that chain. Any applied stress on this configuration of the molecule is then exerted on the C-C bond in the polymer chain backbone and not just on uncoiling the polymer helix in the unstressed state. This results in much higher tensile strength and modulus values. These higher strength and modulus values are desirable in many applications and are seen as an advantage. However, the major disadvantage is that the orientation is thermodynamically unstable. With thermoplastics, such as polyethylene, this means that there are severe temperature limitations to which this oriented material can be used with the improved properties. The key problems to solve are how to put in the orientation, how to relieve any residual stresses from the orientation process, and how to minimize the new limitations of the oriented polymer in use. There is also the variety of orientation processes

that can be used and the limitation of shapes that can be produced by each process. For example, extrusion is one process that can be used. In this instance, the direction of orientation is along the c-axis or the direction of extrusion with little if any orientation along the a- or b-axes, the two other orthogonal directions. The extrusion process makes rod as the simplest shape but can also be used to make profile shapes such as angles, c-channel sections or I-beam sections. The limitation with this process is in size and constant cross-section. Other processes are used to make fibre, wire, pipe and sheet.

The advantage of the oriented fibre made by the gel-spinning process is that high tensile strength and modulus values can be obtained much easier than by any other method to date. The disadvantage of the gel-spinning process is that it is expensive in that it is made from a 10% solution in decalin and that the solvent, which is 90% of the material, has to be processed in making the fibre. Making an oriented fibre from the melt (100% solid) would improve the production economics and work is underway to commercialize such a process. However, to use the oriented fibre for ballistic protection applications, it must be converted into a composite. The composite is made with a polymeric binder as the matrix. In the composite, only about half of the material is the reinforcing oriented fibre and when the composite is in a sheet form, only half of those fibres can be in each of the planar orthogonal directions which means that the strength of the sheet in the planar directions is only a fraction of the strength of the reinforcing fibre. A further concern with oriented fibre reinforced composites, is the separation of the fibres in the woven cloth used in the sheet when the sheet is penetrated by a sharp object instead of stopping the sharp object.

For these reasons, it was decided to investigate the preparation of oriented sheet made directly from solid polyethylene. The two alternatives are a batch process such as forging or a continuous process such as hot-rolling. Woodhams has investigated both at the University of Toronto and it was decided, for economic reasons, to start with the lower cost batch process and see how useful the material formed was. The Woodhams group worked with polyethylene and polypropylene in the hot-rolling process [9]-[11] and with polypropylene in the radial compression process [13]. Because more was known about polyethylene than polypropylene and higher tensile property values are obtained both in theory and in practice, it was decided to make oriented polyethylene sheet by the radial compression or forging process.

Table 1 - The effect of draw ratio on strength and modulus.

Material	Draw Ratio	Ultimate Tensile Strength MPa (p.s.i.)	Young's Modulus GPa (p.s.i.)	Final Thickness mm (in.)
Polyethylene	1	25 (3,600)	0.83 (120,000)	
Oriented Polyethylene	3.1	55 (8,000)	1.48 (215,000)	1.78 (0.070)
Oriented Polyethylene	4.8	70 (10,100)	1.69 (245,000)	1.70 (0.067)
Oriented Polyethylene	7.3	134 (19,500)	2.11 (306,600)	0.89 (0.035)

The next area to be addressed was how much increase in tensile strength and modulus could be obtained by radial compression and how did the results of laboratory scale experiments relate to larger sized samples. The limiting factors in radial compression are in the tonnage of the machine, the size of the plattens, and the height to diameter (aspect) ratio of the rod being compressed. The other critical factor is the draw ratio. Draw ratio, in the case of radial compression, is the square root of the ratio of the original height to the compressed height. In the laboratory, using a 100 ton capacity hydraulic press with 15 cm. x 15 cm. (6" x 6") mild steel plattens, and a 5 cm. (2") diameter

high density polyethylene (HDPE) rod cut to different lengths produced oriented polyethylene sheet with draw ratios and physical properties as seen in Table 1. As can be readily seen, as the draw ratio increases from 1 to 7.3, the ultimate tensile strength increases from 25 MPa (3,600 p.s.i.) to 134 MPa (19,500 p.s.i.) or 5.4 times and the Young's Modulus increases from 0.83 GPa (120,000 p.s.i.) to 2.11 GPa (306,600 p.s.i.) or 2.6 times. These numbers should be viewed as comparative values rather than absolute values. Other important factors, such as molecular weight, have not been optimized in the materials reported in Table 1.

A recent paper by Kortschot [14], indicates that impact strength increases with draw ratio to a maximum and then decreases. The draw ratio range for optimizing impact strength seems to be between 5 and 13 with the maximum at 9.

EXPERIMENTAL

Samples of 152 mm (6") diameter HDPE rod, 133 mm (5.25") and 178 mm (7") long were forged into oriented polyethylene sheet material 4.8 mm (3/16") and 6.4 mm (1/4") thick using a 500 T forging press, and the method described by Bruce [13]. This produced sheets 279 mm (11") by 279 mm (11") with a draw ratio of 5.2 by 5.2. These oriented polyethylene sheets were laminated using the method described by Kortschot [14] to form laminated sheets of 9.5 mm (3/8"), 12.7 mm (1/2") and 19.1 mm (3/4") thicknesses. The 9.5 mm (3/8") laminated sheet was produced from 2 sheets of 4.8 mm (3/16") oriented polyethylene sheet; the 12.7 mm (1/2") laminated sheet from 2 sheets of 6.4 mm (1/4") oriented polyethylene sheet; and the 19.1 mm (3/4") laminated sheet from 3 sheets of 6.4 mm (1/4") oriented polyethylene sheet. 18 laminated sheets were made and delivered to DND for testing. These laminated sheets were trimmed to a size of 20.3 cm (8") by 25.4 cm (10"). There were 6 laminated sheets in each of the three thicknesses. The 9.5 mm (3/8") thick laminated sheets were identified as ADOPAC #1 to #6; the 12.7 mm (1/2") thick laminated sheets were identified as ADOPAC #7 to #12; and the 19.1 mm (3/4") thick laminated sheets were identified as ADOPAC #13 to #18.

HIGH STRAIN RATE TESTING

This work, which DND contracted to the Composites Group in the Department of Metals and Materials at the University of British Columbia [15], involved the effect of loading rate on the ADOPAC oriented polyethylene laminated sheets in comparison with Spectra fibre reinforced composites to assist in predicting the impact resistance of ballistic armours. All properties were measured under both static and dynamic conditions. The testing involved the determination of mechanical properties and the determination of structural behaviour. The determination of mechanical properties included static uniaxial tension and compression tests and dynamic tension and compression tests using two different Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) set-ups [15]. The determination of structural behaviour involved static indentation and deflection tests and instrumented impact tests at intermediate velocities (10 to 100 m/s) and non-instrumented (ballistic) impact tests at high velocities (up to 1000 m/s).

Samples submitted by DND for testing were ADOPAC #4, #8 and #10. ADOPAC #4, which was prepared as a 9.5 mm (3/8") thick sample was measured as 9.8 mm thick. ADOPAC #8 and #10 were prepared as 12.7 mm (1/2") thick samples and were measured as 13.15 and 12.8 mm respectively. The Spectra fibre composite used for comparison was S900 3B made from Spectra 900 fibres and was 9.85 mm thick. The composition of the Spectra 900 composite was 56% (by volume) style 903 fabric and 44% (by volume) Derakane 8084 vinyl ester resin.

DYNAMIC AND STATIC COMPRESSION TESTS

Dynamic and static compression tests were done on samples of ADOPAC and Spectra 900 composites. The results of these tests are summarized in Figures 1, 2, and 3. Results for compression tests on both types of materials are shown in Figure 1. Initial stiffness in compression was 1.5 GPa for both materials. ADOPAC's material ultimate compressive strength (UCS) varied whether or not the sample tested was laminated. The presence of a bonding layer formed during the lamination process resulted in a decrease of the UCS from about 225 MPa to about 140 MPa. The bonding layer serves to maintain the different plates laminated together and to transfer mechanical stresses between them.

Figure 1 - Static compression of ADOPAC and Spectra 900

The remarkable softening effect of the bonding layer is possibly due to a return of the material forming this layer from its oriented state to its original disordered state during the bonding process. With a UCS of 175 MPa, Spectra 900 fall between the two values for ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE. However, for strains up to 20%, Spectra 900 composite shows a higher stress for a given strain. Both materials have a strain to failure of 25%.

Figure 2 - Static and dynamic compression of ADOPAC

Figure 3 - Static and dynamic compression of Spectra 900

The results from the dynamic compression test are displayed on Figure 2 for ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE and on Figure 3 for Spectra 900 composite. Initial stiffness increased from 1.5 to 1.8 GPa in the case of ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE and up to 2.0 GPa for Spectra 900. Ultimate compressive strength for ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE increased by less than 20% at

a strain rate of 4500/s while the increase for Spectra 900 is about 50% even if the imposed strain rate (2400/s) is smaller than the one used for the ADOPAC material. Strain to failure remains unchanged (25%) for ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE but diminished from 25% to 15% for Spectra 900. Compression energies, which are the area under the stress-strain curve, were determined to be 28 J/cc and 30 J/cc in static compression and 33 J/cc and 23 J/cc in dynamic compression for ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE and Spectra composite respectively.

IMPACT TESTING

In order to have a better understanding of ADOPAC's material structural behaviour under ballistic impact conditions, static indentation, static deflection tests, and instrumented impact tests at intermediate velocities (≈ 40 m/s) were conducted. Perforation energies were measured with an instrumented impactor hitting the sample with an approximate velocity of 40 m/s (see Table 2). The results were normalized for panel thickness and were 14.7 J/mm for ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE, 13.7 J/mm for Spectra 900 composite, and 5.4 J/mm for bulk polyethylene (PE). Normalization for thickness supposes a linear relationship between the specimen thickness and the energy absorbed. This assumption is only valid over a narrow range of thicknesses and may not be applicable over the range of thicknesses utilized in the experiments.

Despite the fact that the perforation energy is higher for ADOPAC's material than for Spectra, the energy absorbed for a given displacement is almost twice as much for Spectra than for ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE (see Table 3). The reason why ADOPAC's material absorbs more energy than Spectra is that the former deforms much more before being perforated than the latter. The large deformation of ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE represents a disadvantage of this material for use in structures where the allowed deformation is limited. This is particularly true for body armour applications such as helmets or bullet proof vests, since the deformation of the material, when subjected to a ballistic impact, may cause injuries to the personnel even if the projectile does not perforate the armour. However, since the impact tests were carried out at a velocity much lower than those involved in ballistic impacts, the actual back face deformation of the materials under ballistic impacts could be different than the ones measured.

Table 2 - Maximum absorbed energies for perforation and displacements at maximum energy for impact of 10 cm. x 15 cm. panels over a 7.6 cm. x 12.7 cm. cutout at velocities of ≈ 40 m/s

Material	Thickness (mm)	Max. Energy (J)	Projectile displacement @ max. energy (mm)	Panel deflection @ max. energy (mm)	Energy per thickness (J/mm)
Spectra S900	9.85	135	18.6	6.6	13.7
ADOPAC #4	9.8	150	23.5	11.5	15.3
ADOPAC #8	13.15	185	25.8	10.4	14.1
Polyethylene	6.28	34	22.3	13.8	5.4

It is important to understand that for both materials, actual deformation and therefore, the amount of energy absorbed, depend on the material surface that is free to deform. The smaller the surface, the smaller would be the energy absorbed. This means that ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE cannot be efficient if placed in direct contact with the exterior side of an armour system that does not allow extensive deformation, such as a steel plate. However, ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE

can be efficient if positioned on the interior side of a rigid armour plate, and attached in such a way that a certain amount of deformation is allowed.

Table 3 - Absorbed energies for given projectile displacements for impact of 10 cm. x 15 cm. panels placed over a 7.6 cm. x 12.7 cm. cutout at velocities of ≈ 40 m/s

Material	Thick-ness (mm)	Energy (J) @ 5 mm displ.	Energy per thickness (J/mm)	Energy (J) @ 10 mm displ.	Energy per thickness (J/mm)	Energy (J) @ 15 mm displ.	Energy per thickness (J/mm)
Spectra S900	9.85	48	4.9	86	8.7	120	12.2
ADOPAC #4	9.8	25	2.6	67	6.8	104	10.6
ADOPAC #8	13.15	40	3.0	83	6.3	113	8.6
Polyethylene	6.28	7	1.1	15	2.4	23	3.7

Static perforation tests revealed a reduction of perforation energy by 20% for ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE, 10% for Spectra, and 40% for polyethylene over the values measured in dynamic tests (see Table 4). Increase in penetration energy with loading rate must be due to high strain rate sensitivity of these materials, since the maximum panel deflections were only slightly larger in the static tests.

Table 4 - Maximum absorbed energies for perforation and displacements at maximum energy for static indentation of 6.4 cm. x 6.4 cm. panels placed on a rigid steel plate

Material	Thickness (mm)	Maximum energy (J)	Indenter displ. @ max. energy (Mm)	Panel deflection @ max. energy (mm)	Energy per thickness (J/mm)
Spectra S900	9.85	90	9.85	0	9.1
ADOPAC #4	9.8	45	9.8	0	4.6
ADOPAC #8	13.15	65	13.15	0	4.9
Polyethylene	6.28	9	6.28	0	1.4

OTHER TESTING

The non-high strain rate testing, which was done at Defence Research Establishment Valcartier, is being reported in detail in Part B of this paper which will be presented at the 45th Canadian Chemical Engineering Conference to be held in Quebec City in October 1995. This testing includes the physical characterization, mechanical characterization (other than the high strain rate properties which are reported here), and ballistic evaluation.

CONCLUSIONS

ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE is considered to have a good but not outstanding potential for use as a ballistic protection material, since its high strain rate properties are slightly lower than Spectra 900/Vinylester composite, which represents the lower end of the performance spectrum of high performance polyethylene fibre composites (Dyneema and Spectra fibres). However, as the manufacturing process is new and probably not fully optimized, ADOPAC's material performance in future could possibly be improved to reach that of Spectra 900 composites.

ADOPAC radially oriented HDPE is a promising new candidate material to provide low weight and low cost ballistic protection. However, some improvements have to be achieved before it could be utilized in service. The present results are encouraging enough to justify further development work.

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